

INFLUENCE OF TEXTURE ON THE RESIDUAL STRESS IN 6061Al –15 vol.% SiC_w PM COMPOSITE

Ricardo Fernández^{1*}, Gaspar González-Doncel¹, Giovanni Bruno²

¹ Dept. of Physical Metallurgy, National Center for Metallurgical Research (CENIM), C.S.I.C., Av. de Gregorio del Amo 8, E-28040 Madrid, Spain

² Institut Laue-Langevin, ILL, Rue Jules Horowitz, BP 156F-38042 Grenoble Cedex 9, France

* Present address, Indo SA, Thin Film R&D Department, 08902 L'Hospitalet de l'Obregon, Barcelona, Spain.

SUMMARY: The objective of the present work was to investigate the influence of the texture developed during two different extrusion processes of 6061Al-15 vol.% SiC_w composite (using a flat and a conical die) on the residual stress, RS, generated when a heat treatment for a T6 condition is imposed. The texture and the RS state of 6061Al-15vol%SiC_w composites were determined by x-ray and neutron diffraction, respectively. It was found that even if the texture is indeed changed by the extrusion die shape, the RS is essentially unaffected by this factor. It could then be concluded that the amount of plastic deformation received by the matrix during extrusion and the difference between the physical properties of matrix and reinforcement are decisive for the onset of RS.

KEYWORDS: 6061Al; Texture, Residual Stress, Neutron Diffraction

INTRODUCTION

The fabrication of structural components made from aluminum alloys or aluminum alloy matrix composites usually involves extrusion process and heat treatment as final steps in their fabrication procedure. Because of the extrusion, a strong texture can be developed conferring the component anisotropic properties. The heat treatments typically include a quenching step prior to annealing at moderate temperature to achieve a fully hardened (T6) condition. They lead to the development of a macroscopic residual stress, M-RS [1]. The RS state, which overall may influence severely life service component, is affected by the sample (component) geometry but also by the material microstructure. In particular, the presence of the reinforcing ceramic particles (which leads also to a microscopic residual stress, m-RS, field) and the texture play a major role. The extrusion die geometry is a very important factor influencing the intensity and the components of the texture developed. It has been shown that using dies with different shape-entrances for the extrusion of 6061Al-SiC_w powder blends in the fabrication of discontinuously reinforced metal matrix composites, variations in the final texture components and in their intensity have been obtained [2]. Correspondingly, also changes in the RS state can be also envisaged. In the present investigation PM 6061Al-15 vol.% SiC_w composites have been prepared using two different extrusion dies, namely planar and conical (with an angle of 90°), with the purpose of seeking for differences in the final texture and the resulting RS state developed.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Two composites were prepared by a powder metallurgical route which consisted on the following steps [3]:

1.- Mixing of atomized 6061Al powder supplied by ALPOCO and 15vol.% of Tokai SiC_w powders supplied by Sumitomo in a high energy ball mill for homogenization of the blends.

- 2.- Compaction of the blends at about 300 MPa and 100°C in a special die to produce cylindrical compacts of 200 mm in length and 40 mm in diameter.
- 3.- Vacuum degassing at 500°C of the compacts.
- 4.- Severe extrusion (3.3 true strain) at 500°C for final consolidation in cylindrical bars of 8 mm diameter and 100 mm length.

In the extrusion step, two dies were used in the preparation of the two composites: one with a conical entrance, with a cone angle of 90°, and another one with flat entrance (angle of 180°). Unreinforced 6061Al powder was also processed to have bulk alloys as reference materials. The nomenclature used in designation of materials is as follows: C38 and C08 denote the composite and the un-reinforced alloy extruded with the conical extrusion die and E219 and E220 indicate the composite and the un-reinforced alloy obtained with the flat extrusion die. Table I summarizes the extrusion temperature and the extrusion pressure in the preparation of each material. A heat treatment to reach a T6 condition was imposed. This treatment consists in: a) solution treatment (520°C/90 min), b) quenching in cold water, c) annealing at 146°C, 16 hours for the composites and 56 hours for the alloys.

Texture experiments and analysis.

The x-ray texture measurements were conducted on the Al matrix of all four materials and also on the SiC phase of the two composites. The measurements were carried out by means of the Schulz reflection method as detailed elsewhere [4]. The x-radiation used was $\text{CuK}\alpha$. The samples were tilted at 13 different angles (from 0° to 80°) and rotated from 0° to 360° with a step of 5°. This allowed covering the whole Euler (orientational) space. The pole figures (111), (200), (220), and (311) were measured on small disks where the normal to the surface exposed to the x-rays was parallel to the extrusion axis. From the pole figures and using an appropriate iterative procedure [5], the orientation distribution functions (ODFs), were calculated. Inverse pole figures of the extrusion axis were, then, obtained as projections of the ODFs.

Residual stress experiments and analysis.

The experiments for residual stress determination were conducted by neutron diffraction on REST diffractometer of R2 reactor of Studsvik Neutron Research Laboratory, NFL, Sweden, using a volume of $3 \times 3 \times 3 \text{ mm}^3$. The wavelength used was $\lambda = 1.71 \text{ \AA}$. The samples were cylinders, 6.5 mm diameter and 13 mm height. The reference unstressed samples were loose 6061Al and SiC_w powder. The same heat treatment given to the 6061Al alloy was given to the Al6061 powder to obtain the T6 condition. For this purpose, the powder was sealed in helium atmosphere to minimize oxidation during the solution treatment. The $\sin^2\psi$ method [6] was used, in the ω -mode; *i.e.*, the sample was tilted within the scattering plane. The lattice spacing was plotted versus $\sin^2\psi$ where ψ is the angle between the diffraction vector \mathbf{Q} and the sample axis (extrusion direction). The vector \mathbf{Q} is defined as the difference between scattered and incident wave vectors, $\mathbf{Q} = \mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}_0$, both of modulus $2\pi/\lambda$. The measurements were done at tilt angles ψ between 0° (axial direction) and $\pm 90^\circ$ (radial direction). Further details concerning the geometry of the diffraction experiments are described elsewhere [7]. Because of the strong $\langle 111 \rangle + \langle 100 \rangle$ fiber texture, not all reflections were suitable for strain measurements. It was found that the (311) reflection revealed a good signal to noise ratio, although at only some angles in both the matrix and the reinforcement [7]. The 311 peak has also the advantage of being elastically isotropic. The 2θ angle (with θ the Bragg's angle) for Al and SiC (311) peaks lied around 85°, which ensured a relatively good definition of the gauge volume [8].

Because of the axial symmetry of the extrusion process, a cylindrical coordinate system was adopted, and the geometrical directions were taken as the principal ones. Therefore, the stress tensor components σ_{rad} and σ_{hoop} may be assumed to be equal, because the gage volume was

located in the centre of the sample, but different from σ_{ax} (the stress along the extrusion axis). The evaluation of the stress, though the generalized Hooke's law between strains and stresses [9], was done using plane-specific diffraction elastic constants, EC, as evaluated by means of a Kröner model [10]:

$$E_{311-Al} = 69 \text{ GPa} ; \nu_{311-Al} = 0.35 \quad E_{311-SiC} = 387 \text{ GPa} ; \nu_{311-SiC} = 0.19$$

where E and ν are the Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio, respectively. These elastic constants proved to be very similar to the macroscopic ones.

The rule of mixture, ROM, was then applied to separate M-RS and m-RS from the total (phase specific, index T) stress, according to [11]: $\sigma_{Al/SiC}^T = \sigma^M + \sigma_{Al/SiC}^m$ where, $\sigma^M = (1-f)\sigma_{Al}^T + f\sigma_{SiC}^T$ ($f=0.15$ is the volume fraction of reinforcement). The hydrostatic stress

was, then, calculated as: $\sigma_H = \frac{\sigma_{ax} + 2\sigma_{rad}}{3}$ and the deviatoric one as: $\sigma_{dev} = \sigma_{ax} - \sigma_{rad}$

Figure 1. Micrograph showing the trend of the SiC_w to be aligned with the extrusion axis in the 6061Al-15 vol% SiC_w composites. A more homogeneous distribution results with the conical extrusion die, C38, than with the flat one, E219.

RESULTS

The microstructure of the composite materials is shown in the micrographs of figure 1. A certain trend of the SiC_w to be oriented along the extrusion axis (vertical the figure) can be appreciated in both composites. The distribution of the reinforcement is, however, more homogeneous in the C38 than in the E219 composite. This suggests a less “turbulent” flow of the powder blend during extrusion with the conical than with the flat extrusion die. Also, the aspect ratio of the reinforcement is slightly affected by the extrusion die shape. Whereas in the C38 composite the whisker aspect ratio (length/diameter) is about 4.4, in the E219 this ratio decreases down to 2.1. This also suggests a more severe fragmentation of the reinforcement with the flat extrusion die than with the conical one.

The texture of the two composites and the 6061Al alloys are shown in figure 2. This figure, which shows inverse pole figures of the long extrusion direction, reveals the typical

$\langle 111 \rangle + \langle 001 \rangle$ fiber texture of extruded FCC polycrystalline materials. The volume fraction of $\langle 111 \rangle$ and $\langle 001 \rangle$ grains (textured grains) is summarized in Table I for all four materials. The grain size was $\approx 1.5 \mu\text{m}$ in the composites and slightly larger, about $4 \mu\text{m}$, in the unreinforced alloys.

Several features can be deduced from a comparison of the inverse pole figures of figure 2.

Figure 2. Inverse pole figures showing the texture of the 6061Al matrix of the four materials investigated. C08 and C38 conical die, E220 and E219 flat die.

1.- The addition of SiC reinforcement for composites preparation does produce a decrease in the intensity of the main texture components of the 6061Al phase, as it has been observed in previous work [12]. This decrease is more accentuated in the $\langle 001 \rangle$ (reduction to $\approx 1/3$) than for the $\langle 111 \rangle$ (reduction to $\approx 1/2$) fiber texture components. The reduction factor is essentially independent of the extrusion die shape.

2.- For the unreinforced alloys, the conical die leads to a more intense $\langle 111 \rangle$ component than the flat one. On the contrary, the intensity of the $\langle 001 \rangle$ component is less accentuated with the former than with the latter one. In other words, the intensity ratio of the $\langle 111 \rangle$ component (conical to flat) is about 1.4 whereas it decreases to about 0.8 for the $\langle 001 \rangle$ component. A similar trend is appreciated for the case of the extrusion of the PM composites. An intensity ratio of 1.2 is obtained for the $\langle 111 \rangle$ fiber texture component and 0.6 for the case of the $\langle 001 \rangle$ component. It is worth noting that these data are significantly similar to those obtained for the unreinforced alloys.

3.- The flat die leads to a higher amount of grains oriented along the symmetry boundary [001-111] than the conical die, in both the 6061Al alloy and in the composites (residual grains). In other words, more texture components are observed after extrusion with the flat die.

Extr.die	material	code	Extr. temp.(°C)	Extr. pres.(MPa)	$V_f^{Al} < 111 >$ (%)	$V_f^{Al} < 001 >$ (%)
Conical	6061Al	C08	525	408	68	30
	6061Al-15 vol% SiC _w	C38	498	560	45	12
Flat	6061Al	E220	490	543	56	35
	6061Al-15 vol% SiC _w	E219	480	669	41	17

Table I. Extrusion temperature, extrusion pressure, percentage of the 6061Al grains oriented within the main texture components, $V_f^{Al} < 111 >$ and $V_f^{Al} < 001 >$, in all four materials investigated (calculated with a tolerance of 10°).

Figure 3.- Inverse pole figures of the SiC phase in the C38 (conical die) and E219 (flat die) composites (extrusion axis direction).

Further interesting features are also deduced when the texture of the SiC_w phase is analyzed, figure 3. The texture of the reinforcing SiC_w phase is related to the misalignment of the short fibers because the long direction of the single crystal whiskers is coincident with a crystallographic $<111>$. The texture of this phase gives, hence, hints on the realignment process of the ceramic reinforcement during material flow through the extrusion die. It has been shown in previous investigations that most of the SiC_w reinforcement remains randomly oriented in the composite [12]. The alignment of the remaining SiC_w obeys a Gaussian behavior, $I(\alpha) = a \exp(-b\alpha^2)$, where $I(\alpha)$ is the diffracted intensity of the (111) reflection as a function of α , the angle between the extrusion axis and the long whisker direction, and a and b fitting parameters, specific of the SiC whisker alignment in each composite. These constants, obtained after curve fitting of the experimental data, are given in Table II. Similarly, the remaining random population of reinforcement is given as a constant I_o , also listed in Table II. The variation of the density of orientations of SiC with α , $\rho(\alpha)$, is given as, $\rho(\alpha) = 2\pi \sin(\alpha) I(\alpha)$. By appropriate integration of this function the percentage of whiskers which is aligned with the extrusion axis can be deduced. The values obtained are also summarized in Table II. As can be seen, the conical die results in a higher volume fraction of SiC_w particles aligned with the long extrusion axis than the flat one. This is more clearly seen in figure 4, where the density distribution of random and oriented SiC_w of the C38 and E219 composites are plotted.

Composite code	a	b	I_o	F_v (%)
----------------	-----	-----	-------	-----------

C38 (conical die)	2.51	17.55	0.646	31
E219 (flat die)	3.69	27.69	0.871	23

Table II. Fitting parameters, a and b of the Gaussian distribution of the oriented population of the reinforcement, I_o values corresponding to the random population of the reinforcement, and percentage of whiskers aligned with the extrusion axis, F_v , in the two composites.

Figure 4.- One-dimensional pole figure of the SiC comparing the orientation density of the SiC_w in the C38 and E219 composites (flat vs. conical). The oriented and random populations of whiskers are described by the density functions $I(\alpha) = a \exp(-b\alpha^2) \sin \alpha$, and $I(\alpha) = I_o \sin \alpha$, respectively. The values of I_o are summarized in Table II.

material	Al Phase				SiC Phase			
	Axial	Radial	Dev.	Hydr.	Axial	Radial	Dev.	Hydr.
C08	113	80	33	91	-	-	-	-
E220	119	85	33	97	-	-	-	-
C38	188	141	47	157	-293	-183	-110	-219
E219	239	218	21	225	-348	-227	-121	-267

Table III. Total axial and radial (MPa) as well as deviatoric, (taken as $\Delta\sigma = \sigma_{ax} - \sigma_{rad}$) and hydrostatic ($\sigma_{ax} = 1/3(\sigma_{ax} + 2\sigma_{rad})$) residual stress for the Al and SiC phase of all materials errors are of the order of 7 MPa for the Al phase and 15 MPa for the SiC phase).

Figure 5.- Strain vs. $\sin^2\psi$ plots showing the residual strain state in the C08 and E220 alloys, as well that in the C38 and E219 composites, Al and SiC phases.

The results of the RS analysis are summarized in the strain vs. $\sin^2\psi$ plots of figure 5. From these 'raw data' the total stresses can be directly calculated (using Hooke's law) and they are shown in Table III. From both figure 5 and Table III it can be seen that all components of the

total RS are higher in the composites than in the alloys. This is because of the contribution of both M-RS and m-RS in the composites. Only M-RS is developed in the alloys. The total RS state possesses both hydrostatic and deviatoric character. In the alloys, the latter is present because the samples shape influences the M-RS; *i.e.*, the boundary conditions are different from the axial to the radial and hoop direction [13]. In the composites, another contribution has to be considered: the fraction of SiC_w aligned with the extrusion axis also confers a deviatoric character to the m-RS. It is also seen that the magnitude of the RS is virtually identical in the two alloys whereas in the composites a slight difference can be appreciated: the deviatoric stress is higher in the C38 composite than in the E219, while the hydrostatic stress is sensibly higher in E219.

DISCUSSION

It has been observed that the texture is always more intense in the unreinforced alloys than in the composites, regardless of the extrusion die shape. This phenomenon has been attributed to the occurrence of particle stimulation nucleation, PSN, for recrystallisation at the Al-SiC interface [12]. This is a process, which tends to randomize the deformation texture resulting from extrusion. Since this process is absent in the 6061Al alloys, the <111>+<001> fibre texture components are more intense in the alloys than in the composites. Unsurprisingly, the PSN process induced by the presence of the SiC reinforcement is not affected by the extrusion die geometry. It is a process linked strictly to the interaction at the Al-SiC interface.

Material	M-RS (MPa)				m-RS, 6061Al (MPa)				m-RS, SiC (MPa)			
	Ax	Rad	Dev	Hydr	Ax	Rad	Dev	Hydr	Ax	Rad	Dev	Hydr
C38	116	77	39	90	72	64	8	67	-409	-260	-149	-309
E219	151	138	12	143	88	80	8	82	-499	-365	-134	-410

Table IV. Macroscopic and microscopic residual stress (Axial, radial, deviatoric, hydrostatic) of the two composites, all after the T6 heat treatment. Errors are of the order of 10 MPa for the Al phase and 15 to 25 MPa for the SiC phase.

After separation of the total RS into M-RS and m-RS, several additional features of the RS state can be deduced. The data resulting from this separation is summarized in Table IV. As it has been already summarized in previous works [1,13], the M-RS of the composites is mostly hydrostatic, and higher in the alloy than in the composites in agreement with the higher CTE of the former [14]. The m-RS is tensile in the matrix and compressive in the reinforcement, and is also strongly hydrostatic because the SiC is mostly randomly oriented. The deviatoric term is due to the population of short SiC fibers aligned with the extrusion axis. The m-RS is slightly modified by the different volume fraction of reinforcement of the two composites and because of the different aspect ratio of the SiC_w, Table I. This difference, together with the higher SiC_w aspect ratio in the former than in the latter composite, justifies the slightly higher deviatoric total-RS of the composite extruded with the conical than with the flat die. The measurements of the SiC phase in sample C38 show a larger error bar than those on the E219, as the strain vs. $\sin^2\psi$ curve is unexpectedly essentially constant for C38. This induces larger uncertainties in the determination of both the M-RS and the m-RS of the 6061Al phase. However, the stronger hydrostatic character of the m-RS and M-RS in E219 is clear from Table IV. This implies that the larger fraction of randomly oriented particles indeed influences the RS state of the composites, since the RS is essentially identical in the unreinforced alloys. Therefore, we can deduce that there is a basic absence of 6061Al texture

effect on this RS state, at least at the level of the differences in texture appreciated. This is fully confirmed by the data of the unreinforced alloys E220 and C08.

While the texture seems to play a limited role if its variation is not significant, like in the present case, the microstructure and the temperature drop seem to have a decisive influence on the RS state. The first acts via the type and magnitude of plastic deformation (axial) undergone by the materials during extrusion, the second acts via the difference in the physical properties of the two phases.

CONCLUSIONS

In this work the analysis of the texture and its influence on the residual stress state of PM 6061Al-15vol%SiC_w composites, as obtained by extrusion utilizing a conical and a flat extrusion die, has been conducted.

The following are the main conclusions that can be drawn from the present research.

- 1.- With both extrusion dies, a strong $\langle 111 \rangle + \langle 001 \rangle$ fiber texture of the 6061Al matrix is developed in the composites and the unreinforced alloys. The conical die leads to the strongest $\langle 111 \rangle$ fiber texture component whereas the flat die to the $\langle 001 \rangle$ one.
- 2.- The conical die leads also to a higher percentage of whiskers aligned with the extrusion axis direction than the flat one, 31% vs. 23%. This is consistent with the more “lamellar” flow with the conical die than with the flat one, allowing a better re-alignment of the whiskers during extrusion reduction.
- 3.- A deviatoric RS state is developed due to sample geometry and to the fraction of SiC_w aligned with the extrusion axis. The hydrostatic total, macro and micro residual stress are larger in E219 (flat die) than in C38 (conical die), but essentially identical in the corresponding unreinforced alloys (E220 and C08, respectively). Therefore the distribution of the reinforcement and perhaps other microstructural parameters, like the different aspect ratio, more than the texture, plays the decisive role to determine the RS state.
- 4.- The plastic deformation during extrusion induces an alignment of the particles with the extrusion axis. This and the temperature drop during quenching create the final RS state decided by the (macro and micro) RS state, through the differences in physical properties (Young’s modulus and coefficient of thermal expansion) between the two phases.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Project MAT01-2085 from MCYT, Spain, and support from NFL (Studsвик) under contract nº N01 HPRI-CT-1999-00061 in the frame of ARI Program.

REFERENCES

- [1] R.Fernández, G.Bruno, G.Gonzalez-Doncel, Acta Mater.52 (2004) 5471-5483.
- [2] R.Fernández, Ph. D. Thesis, Complutense University, Madrid, Spain. (2003).
- [3] A.Borrego, J.Ibañez, V.López, M.Lieblich, G.González-Doncel, Scripta Mater. 34 (1996) 471-478.
- [4] M.T.Pérez-Prado, M.C. Cristina, O. Ruano, and G. González-Doncel, Mater. Sci. and Eng. 244A (1998) 216-223.
- [5] H.J. Bunge, Texture Analysis in Materials Science, Butterworths, London (1982).
- [6] H. Dölle, V. Hauk. Z. Metallkunde 69 (1978) 410.

- [7] R. Fernández, G. Bruno, A. Borrego, G. González-Doncel and A. Pyzalla. *Appl. Phys. A* 74 (2002) S1146.
- [8] P.C.Brand, H.J.Prask, *J.Appl.Cryst.* 27 (1994) 164-176
- [9] W.F. Hosford, *The mechanics of crystals and textures polycrystals*, Oxford Univ. Press, Oxford, UK, 1993.
- [10] E. Kröner, *Z f Phys.* 151 (1958) 504.
- [11] L.Pintschovius, in: M.T.Hutchings, A.D.Krawitz (Eds.), *Measurement of Residual and Applied Stress Using Neutron Diffraction*, NATO advanced research workshop, Kluwer Academics, Dordrecht, 1992, pp. 115-130.
- [12] A.Borrego, R.Fernández, M.C.Cristina, J.Ibañez, and G.González-Doncel: *Comp.Sci.Technol.*, 62 (2002), 731-742.
- [13] P. Fernández, G.González-Doncel, G.Bruno, this volume
- [14] G.Bruno, R. Fernández, G.González-Doncel, *Mater. Sci. Eng. A382* (2004) 188-197.
- [15] A.L Geiger, J.A. Walker, *JOM*, 45 (1991) 8.